

THE ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AMONG CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE PATIENT REGARDING THEIR DISEASE

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Abstract

Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a progressive lung disease characterized by air flow obstruction and breathing difficulties. Major causative factor includes smoking history. Patient knowledge about risk factors is mandatory to prevent or delay progression of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Aim: The purpose of this study was to assess the knowledge among chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient regarding their disease.

Method: A descriptive study with random sampling technique were utilized. Questionnaire were distributed among participants, the questionnaire consists of two portion, portion A has question regarding sociodemographic characteristics and portion B has questions specific to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (in native language of the participants).

Results: The data collected was analyzed through SPSS version 21. The data collected from the participants were illustrated through tables and bar charts. As from demographics, total subject of the study was 130, out of which 87 participants were male and 43 were female. Majority of them (64) had age above 45 years, followed by 62 who had age between 31 to 45 years, and remaining 4 participants had age between 25 to 30 years.

Conclusion: The present study findings confirmed that total knowledge level of the participants about their disease was poor. Higher knowledge level was found in areas about signs and symptoms of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and risk factors like smoking that can cause chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Knowledge related the management of COPD was reported poor and even most of the patient were not aware that Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can be prevented.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a common and slowly progressing disease characterized by persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow

limitation due to airway or alveolar abnormalities (Lu, Zeng et al. 2021). Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a broad term that results in inflammatory condition involving the

airways, lung parenchyma, and pulmonary vasculature (Poto, Loffredo et al. 2022). It is thought that possible pathological explanation behind it is oxidative stress and protease-anti protease imbalances. Neutrophils and macrophages are recruited and release multiple inflammatory mediators, this means there is an involvement of immune system. The smallest microscopic structure in the lungs which are called alveoli is damage by oxidative stress and excess protease activity (Bezerra, Lanzetti et al. 2023). The pathological activity mediated by protease results in the destruction of elastin, which further leads to loss of elastic recoil and its consequences include an airway collapse during exhalation (Kansal, Chopra et al. 2023). According to statistics, COPD was ranked eighth as a cause of disease burden as measured by disability-adjusted life years by the Global Burden of Disease Study in 2015 (Li, Cao et al. 2020). comparatively chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is common in women than in men, with the rate of death from this severely progressive condition which is called COPD, among women predicted to overtake that of men in the next few years (Buttery, Zysman et al. 2021).

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a condition of the lung which caused damage to the airways or other parts of the lung that blocks airflow and causes breathing difficulty (Rao, Karindas et al. 2022). *Some of their features by means of which chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is diagnoses are;* shortness of breath (dyspnea) and cough, which may or may not be productive (PRASAD 2020). Even though chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is not curable, but preventive and manageable by avoiding these causative factors like avoid smoking, avoiding air pollution and getting vaccines (Can and Will 2021). Treatment options for COPD includes; medicines, oxygen and pulmonary rehabilitation (Wytrychowski, Hans-Wytrychowska et al. 2020). Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), a global health problem, is gradually increasing (PRASAD 2020). Some of the surveys revealed that chronic obstructive pulmonary disease would be third cause of death, even in developed countries it is estimated that 10% of its occurrence potential (Adeloye, Song et al. 2022). Globally, it is calculated that chronic obstructive pulmonary disease may affect 380 million people leading to 3 million deaths yearly (Viegi, Maio

et al. 2020). A major epidemiological survey in the middle East and North Africa area (BREATHE) performed in 11 countries found that the incidence of COPD was 2.1% among Pakistani people over the age of 40 (Khan 2022).

The statistic of pulmonary disease is increasing in Pakistan due to the lack of knowledge among general population regarding the risk factors that leads to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Knowledge regarding risk factors may prevent people from getting chronic pulmonary disease. Smoking is considered to be the major cause of pulmonary disease, thus to eliminate these risk factors from society, it is needed to research this issue in patient with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a progressive inflammatory lung disease that affect air ways and is featured by air flow obstruction that results in dyspnea (difficulty in breathing), cough with sputum production. All these symptoms lead to impairment of quality of life, may cause disability. Risk factors include smoking, and environmental factors. Because it is completely preventable. Knowledge of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is essential for its prevention. Therefore, it is needed to be research this issue among patient which suffering from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

1.3 SIGNIFICANT OF STUDY

This study will be helpful for the health care worker, doctor and nurse to pay more attention to teach patient about prevention of respiratory disease which due to tobacco, especially among chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

1.4: Aim of the study

The aim of the study is the assessment of knowledge of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient regarding their disease.

1.5: Objective

To assess the knowledge of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient regarding their disease.

1.6: Research Question

What is the level of knowledge of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient regarding their disease?

1.7: Operational definition

Knowledge will be assessed through an adopted, modified and translated questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of 13 items ranging on nominal scale. The participants who will tick the right option will be given 1 mark. The score may vary from 0 to 13. The higher number indicate higher level of knowledge.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a group of progressive lung diseases; it is usually the combination of the two pulmonary conditions that are emphysema and chronic bronchitis (PRASAD 2020). Two pathological factors for its explanation are oxidative stress and excess protease activity (Jasemi, Khazaei et al. 2022). Inflammation causes by oxidative stress and excess protease activity leads to loss of elastic recoil of alveoli., due to which while exhalation this results in airway collapsing. The trajectory of COPD can be daunting for both patients and clinicians (Burke 2020). According to World Health Organization (WHO) chronic obstructive pulmonary disease as an underdiagnosed, life-threatening progressive disease of the lungs, not curable, and is characterized by chronic airflow obstruction hampering the normal breathing (Szalontai, Gémes et al. 2021).

As inference from previous study conducted on patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. This was cross sectional study approach. Total of 14 patient of COPD were participated in the study. The participants were selected through convenient sampling technique. The goal of the study was to assess the knowledge, attitude and behavior about the disease process and physiotherapy management in patients diagnosed with COPD. Findings of the study revealed that there is insufficient knowledge with patients regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Their attitude was negative, and flawed behavior. Even it was found that none of the participants had knowledge about the term “chronic obstructive pulmonary disease”, reflecting there poor knowledge (Aldhahir, Alqahtani et al. 2022).

Another study conducted on 389 Canadians were surveyed who were 40 years of age and older, physician diagnosed with COPD, and current or former smokers. The purpose of this study was to determine whether Canadians with COPD are knowledge and supported, and to recommend solutions to any care gaps identified. It was concluded that studies population had unsatisfactory level of knowledge about the management of COPD and little contact with lung health educators. Based on findings the study recommend that conduction of awareness programs on COPD management, self-specific care, and self-management education may help improve knowledge regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients (Hernandez, Balter et al. 2009).

In China, a study with cross sectional approach was conducted in December 2021. The study aimed to assess knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease among high-risk population for COPD. This study was done in a tertiary care hospital in Chongqing. Total of 241 subject were participated in the study. As inference form study statistics, participants had moderate level of knowledge regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease prevention. And it was also revealed that participants had less understating on vaccination and lung function tests but had an active attitude towards health. Among the people at risk of COPD, 76.8% experienced a moderate level of knowledge, attitude, and practice toward COPD prevention, while 22.0% were at a poor level (Zhao and Zhao 2023).

Another study conducted at Sednawy in Zagazig Hospital. This is descriptive study approach; the participants were selected through purposive sampling technique. Total of 60 elderly subjects were included. The aim of this study is to assess knowledge and practices regarding COPD among elderly patients. The study conclude that participants had poor level of knowledge and practice regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (EmanShokryAbd-Allah and ElsayedElshora 2021).

An online survey conducted by a steering committee of American Thoracic Society clinicians and scientists, through an online source of Harris Poll Online panel, a COPD subject were analyzed. The

aim of the study was to investigate subjects' COPD knowledge, including education they receive from health care providers, treatment experiences, and practices with inhalation devices. It was statistically reported that participants had 45% and 44% level of knowledge regarding symptoms and causes of COPD(Dhand, Mahler et al. 2018).

Hence the above mentioned study confirms that patient with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease had poor knowledge regarding their disease. So it is needed to research this issue again to assess the level of knowledge among chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

A descriptive cross sectional research study design will be used.

3.2 Setting

The study sitting will be tertiary care hospital Lahore.

3.3 Sampling Technique

Random sampling technique will be used.

3.4 Sample size

The sample size will be calculated through slovin's formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n= Sample size

N= Population size

e= Level of precision/ margin of erro3.5 Eligibility criteria:

3.5.1 Inclusion criteria:

Our study includes those chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients visiting outpatient department of tertiary care hospital of Lahore.

3.5.2 Exclusion criteria

Our study excluded chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient outside hospital, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient in emergency department and non-chronic obstructive pulmonary disease inside the hospital:

3.6 Ethical consideration:

The ethical consideration will be followed which is set by committee of nursing department, superior university, participant will be ensure for data privacy and they are not forced to participate in this study. Participant will be given enough information regarding study and their participation in this study. There will be no harm, therefore, confidentiality will be maintained.

3.7 Data Collection Tool

Data has been gathered by using an adapted version of tool to assess the level of knowledge regarding respiratory disease among chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients.

3.8 Data Collection Procedure

Data has been gathered from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient those visiting to outpatient department of tertiary care hospital in Lahore.

3.9 Population of study

Our study population is chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient visiting outpatient department in tertiary care hospital of Lahore.

3.10 Duration of the study

The study has taken approximately 9 months.

RES LUTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics of study population

Table No: 1

Gender				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	87	65.4	66.9	66.9

female	43	32.3	33.1	100.0
Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 1

As mentioned in the above table #1 the frequency and percentage of male and female(gender) based distribution of participant. Out of 130 participant

87(66.9%) were male and 43(33.1%) of the participant were female.

Table No: 2

		Age			
Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	25-30 years	4	3.0	3.1	3.1
	31-45 years	62	46.6	47.7	50.8
	45 above	64	48.1	49.2	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 2

According to the above table & fig #2, the age of the participant, the frequency of the participant who aged 25-30 years is 4(3.1%), 31-45 years is 62(47.7%)

and those who had aged above 45 years is 64(49.2%) out of 130 total participants.

Knowledge score of the subject regarding Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Table No: 3

People with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease may feel shortness of breath.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	85	63.9	65.4	65.4
	No	45	33.8	34.6	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 3

In response to a question related to signs and symptoms of COPD that is “People with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease may feel shortness of breath”. Out of 130 total participants, the frequency

of subject who responds correctly (Yes) is 85(65.4%), while those who responds incorrectly (No) is 45(34.6%).

Table No: 4

People with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease often have a cough that would not go away.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	88	66.2	67.7	67.7
	No	42	31.6	32.3	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 4

Table and fig#4 show the patient response to pulmonary disease often have a cough that would not go away”. Which indicates that the frequency of participant who responds correctly (Yes) is

question that “People with chronic obstructive 88(67.7%), while a minor number of participant response incorrectly (No) is 42(32.3%).

Table No: 5

Cigarette smoking or secondhand smoke cause most of the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	67	50.4	51.5	51.5
	No	63	47.4	48.5	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 5

Question about tobacco substance use and their relation to lung disease such as “Cigarette smoking or secondhand smoke cause most of the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease”. Approximately half

of the subject 63(48.5%) responds incorrectly (No), while 67(51.5%) of the subject responds correctly out of 130 subjects.

Table No: 6

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can be prevented.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	67	50.4	51.5	51.5
	No	63	47.4	48.5	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 6

The above table #6 show the subject response to question that “Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can be prevented”. The frequency of subject

who responds correctly (yes) is 67(51.5%), similarly the frequency of subject who responds incorrectly (No) is 63(48.5%).

Table No: 7

People with COPD should have a flu shot every year.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	84	63.2	64.6	64.6
	No	46	34.6	35.4	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 7

According to above table #7 which indicates, the participant response to question that “People with COPD should have a flu shot every year”. The

majority of subject responds correctly (Yes) 84(64.6%), while others respond incorrectly (No) 46(35.4%).

Table No: 8

The use oxygen at home can help people with COPD live longer.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	77	57.9	59.2	59.2
	No	53	39.8	40.8	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 8

In response to a question that “The use oxygen at home can help people with COPD live longer”. Here we can see that majority of subject responds correctly

(Yes) is 77(59.2%), and some of them respond incorrectly (No) is 53(40.8%).

Table No: 9

The medicine albuterol (inhaler)can be used every time you have shortness of breath.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	66	49.6	50.8	50.8
	No	64	48.1	49.2	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 9

As shown above in the table & Fig #9, the subject response to question that “The medicine albuterol (inhaler)can be used every time you have shortness of

breath”. The frequency of subject who responds correctly (Yes) is 66(50.8%), while those who responds incorrectly (No) is 64(49.2%).

Table No: 10

COPD can be reversed					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	77	57.9	59.2	59.2
	No	53	39.8	40.8	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 10

Most of the subject response to question that “COPD can be reversed” was incorrect. The frequency of subject who respond correctly (No) is

53(40.8%), while those who respond incorrectly (Yes) is 77(59.2%), out of 130 subjects.

Table No: 11

People with COPD should get a pneumonia shot					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	64	48.1	49.2	49.2
	No	66	49.6	50.8	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 11

As shown in the above table #11 the subject response to question that “People with COPD should get a pneumonia shot”. Approximately half of the subject

respond correctly (Yes) 64(49.2%), while remaining of the subject respond correctly (No) 66(50.8%).

Table No: 12

People can stop taking their long-acting breath medicine (inhaler)when their COPD symptom get better.					
Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Yes	75	56.4	57.7	57.7
	No	55	41.4	42.3	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 12

As shown above in the table #12, the subject response to question that “People can stop taking their long-acting breath medicine (inhaler)when their COPD symptom get better”. Majority of the subject

respond correctly (Yes) is 75(57.7%), while other respond incorrectly (No) 55(42.3%).

Table No: 13

People should only use their COPD inhaler (medicine)when they cannot breath.					
Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Yes	89	66.9	68.5	68.5
	No	41	30.8	31.5	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 13

The subject’s response to question that “People should only use their COPD inhaler (medicine) when they cannot breathe”. Here we can see in the table#13

that, The majority of the participant respond correctly (Yes) is 89(68.5%), while others respond incorrectly (No) is 41(31.5%).

Table No: 14

Stopping smoking will prevent COPD from getting worse.					
Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Yes	91	68.4	70.0	70.0
	No	39	29.3	30.0	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 14

When subjects were asked that smoking cessation will prevent COPD “Stopping smoking will prevent COPD from getting worse”. The frequency of

participant who responds correctly (Yes) is 91(70.0%), while those who respond incorrectly (No) is 39(30.0%) out of 130 subjects.

Table No: 15

COPD medicine keep the disease from getting worse.					
Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Yes	86	64.7	66.2	66.2
	No	44	33.1	33.8	100.0
	Total	130	97.7	100.0	

Fig: 15

According to the above table and fig#15 which indicates the patient response to a question that “COPD medicine keep the disease from getting worse”. The frequency of subject who respond

correctly (Yes) is 86(66.2%), while those who respond incorrectly (No) is 44(33.8%) out of 130 subjects.

Table No: (1) Sociodemographic Characteristics of study participants

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male		87	65.4	66.9	66.9
female		43	32.3	33.1	100.0
Total		130	97.7	100.0	

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
25-30 years		4	3.0	3.1	3.1
31-45 years		62	46.6	47.7	50.8
45 above		64	48.1	49.2	100.0
Total		130	97.7	100.0	

Table No: (2) Distribution of the participant based on response to knowledge questions.

Knowledge Questions	Yes (%)	No (%)
People with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease may feel shortness of breath.	85 (65.4%)	45 (34.6%)
People with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease often have a cough that would not go away.	88 (67.7%)	42 (32.3%)

Cigarette smoking or secondhand smoke cause most of the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.	67 (51.5%)	63 (48.5%)
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can be prevented	67 (51.5%)	63 (48.5%)
People with COPD should have a flu shot every year.	84 (64.6%)	46 (35.4%)
The use oxygen at home can help people with COPD live longer.	77 (59.2%)	53 (40.2%)
The medicine albuterol (inhaler) can be used every time you have shortness of breath	66 (50.8%)	64 (49.2%)
COPD can be reversed	77 (59.2%)	53 (40.8%)
People with COPD should get a pneumonia shot	64 (49.2%)	66 (50.8%)
People can stop taking their long-acting breath medicine (inhaler) when their COPD symptom get better	75 (57.7%)	55 (42.3%)
People should only use their COPD inhaler (medicine) when they cannot breathe	89 (68.5%)	41 (31.5%)
Stopping smoking will prevent COPD from getting worse.	91 (70.0%)	39 (30.0%)
COPD medicine keep the disease from getting worse	86 (66.2%)	44 (33.8%)

DISCUSSION

The purpose of recent study is to assess the knowledge level among chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) patient regarding their disease. The sociodemographic statistics of our study as; out of total 130 patients, 87(66.9%) were male & 43(33.1%) were female. The frequency of subject by age distribution as; 4(3.1%) was from aged 25-30 years, 62(47.7%) was from aged 31-45 years, and 64(49.2%) was from aged 45 years above.

The present study revealed that, half of the subject 48(36.9%) had poor level of knowledge and half of them had acceptable level of knowledge regarding their disease. The overall turnover of knowledge was considered insufficient. As from results portion of the study most of the study participant’s (89) belief that people can only use inhaler when they cannot breathe, logistically which is wrong, because chronic

obstructive pulmonary disease required continuous management. Similarly, when asked about pneumonia shot indication “People with COPD should get a pneumonia shot”, highest portion (66) considered pneumonia shot unnecessary. Not even that most of the study subject response was unexpected to a question about the prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease that is “Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can be prevented”, about 63 subject respond incorrectly. However, when asked that stopping smoking will prevent chronic obstructive pulmonary disease worsening, majority of them (91) agreed to given statement, reflecting subject awareness of its causation factor. So, the response to some question, particularly about prevention and treatment adherence, reflect low level of knowledge of the study participants.

A study with qualitative approach was conducted in India. The study aimed to investigate the knowledge, attitude and behavior about the disease process among chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. 14 patients were included through convenient sampling technique; data collection takes 6 months. From results portion of the study it was found that there is a negligence about the disease process, causation factors were unknown to most of the study participants. Even none of the study subject were aware about the term “Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease”. The study concluded that there is a lack of knowledge, negative attitude, and even majority of subject does not know about the proper management of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. The study emphasized on information accessibility through awareness program or proper educational framework to rise knowledge and improve behavioral modification of the people regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease(Gupta, Ravaliya et al. 2019).

Another study conducted on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient in United states. The aim of which was to assess the knowledge and prevalence of co-existing condition occur with COPD among COPD patient. It was done through telephone in 2006 on 1003 patient. As inference from different question that were asked, it was concluded that there is a lack of self-knowledge regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease among studied population. it was also noted that even COPD was undertreated by most of the patients, reflecting their miss management for COPD, which could otherwise be life-threatening(Barr, Celli et al. 2009).

A study published by Dimitrios G. Raptis, Georgia G. Rapti et. All. The purpose of which was to assess the knowledge of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patient and care givers regarding COPD. A Bristol COPD knowledge questionnaire was used in the study. The study used a previous pre assess information, that the lack of education among disease suffer is the basic reason behind its burden in the society. Like above mention studies, this study also concluded the lack of knowledge among patient with COPD, care givers and volunteers. Thus, emphasizing the need for educational program on the issue mention(Raptis, Rapti et al. 2022).

A cross sectional study conducted on patient with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. The study aimed to assess the knowledge of patient and their resident proxies regarding chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. About 37 statement related to generic health and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease were asked from both patient and their proxies. The response to statement were classified as; true, false and did not know. Only 34 % of accurate responses were noted between both patient itself and their proxies to a given questionnaire. The study stated that overall knowledge level was insufficient between both group towards chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and rise the need for educational framework to improve awareness about chronic obstructive pulmonary disease(Nakken, Janssen et al. 2017).

In China, a study was done through multi stage stratified cluster sampling from 125 surveillance points in 31 provinces (autonomous regions, municipalities) in 2014-2015. The study aimed to understand the awareness of COPD and its related knowledge among patient with the same diagnose. The total number of subject were 75107, but only 9132 were included in the study. A multi variant logistic regression analysis show that the overall awareness rate of COPD is co linked with the knowledge regarding chronic respiratory disease history, symptoms, causes and occupational dust exposure. It was also stated that the educational level of the study participants also had impact on COPD related knowledge. the study concluded that there was unsatisfactory level of knowledge among studied population in China(Cong, Yao et al. 2020).

Conclusion

The present study findings confirmed that total knowledge level of the participants about their disease was poor. Higher knowledge level was found in areas about signs and symptoms of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and risk factors like smoking that can cause chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Knowledge related the management of COPD was reported poor and even most of the patient were not aware that Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can be prevented.

Limitations of the study

Patients fear about identity exposure and hospital strict regulations was the factors that cause difficulty with the present study data collection.

Recommendations

Due to the current findings of the study, it is enforced that people must be educated about the preventive ways that can be done for Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, must be tell about smoking impact on lungs and their possible negative consequences. There must be educational program for affected population, that can tell them how to manage COPD signs and symptoms because COPD is lifelong disease.

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